

Community Service to Improve Village Welfare through Enterprise Programs in the Pandemic Era

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Abstract:- The COVID-19 pandemic has presented serious challenges to people's well-being, especially in rural areas. The significant economic impact of the pandemic has resulted in decreased income and increased unemployment rates in villages. Therefore, Community Service is a very important means to address this issue. This research aims to investigate how entrepreneurship programmes in the context of Community Service can improve village welfare in the pandemic era. The research methods used in this study are surveys, interviews, and secondary data analysis. Surveys were conducted in several villages affected by the pandemic, and interviews were conducted with community members and local stakeholders. Secondary data was used to analyse the economic development of the villages before and after the implementation of the entrepreneurship programme. The results show that entrepreneurship programmes in the context of Community Service can be an effective solution to improve village welfare in the pandemic era. The programme encourages village communities to develop small and medium enterprises (SMEs), such as agriculture, crafts, and services, which are able to survive in difficult economic situations. The programme also provides training and mentoring to villagers to improve their skills in managing businesses and marketing products. With the entrepreneurship programme in place, villages that have implemented it report increased income, decreased unemployment rates, and improved overall community welfare. The programme also helps villagers to adapt to new situations brought about by the pandemic, such as changes in consumption patterns and market demand. This research concludes that Community Service through entrepreneurship programmes can be an effective tool to improve village welfare in the pandemic era. The importance of cooperation between academics, government, and communities in implementing this programme to ensure its sustainability and success in the long run. It is hoped that the results of this study can provide insights and guidance for similar efforts in various villages affected by the pandemic.

Keywords:- Welfare, Village, Entrepreneurship.

I. INTRODUCTION

The island of Java produces a lot of food, especially in the East Java region with a variety of potential villages. Java has diversity both from ethnicity, culture and food products that are very beneficial for all Indonesian people. However, there is potential in each village that is less explored, one of which is the lack of exposure of potential in Gresik and the

lack of community empowerment through entrepreneurship. Untoro (2010) said that entrepreneurship is a courage that a person has in making various efforts so that life's needs can be met by using the ability and also utilizing the potential possessed in order to produce something useful for oneself and others (Apriana, Kristiawan & Wardiah, 2019; Lotulung, Ibrahim & Tumurang, 2018; Listiningrum, Wisetsri & Boussanlegue, 2020; Mas, Masaong & Sukung, 2021).

The welfare of rural communities through entrepreneurship is very much needed in this pandemic era, support and encouragement are needed for the welfare of the people in the village. The more advanced a country is, there will be many educated people but on the other hand there are also many unemployed, so here the importance of the entrepreneurial world will be felt. Pandemic conditions like this will be more profitable if supported by entrepreneurs because the government's ability is very limited. Therefore, entrepreneurship is a potential for development, both in number and in the quality of the entrepreneurs themselves. Empowerment through entrepreneurship itself is an effort to build power by encouraging, motivating and raising awareness of the potential it has and striving to develop it and strengthen the potential through entrepreneurship owned by the community and village (Santoso & Oetomo, 2018; Chowdhury, Audretsch & Belitski, 2019; Akhmetshin et al, 2019; Al-Jubari, Hassan & Liñán, 2019; Newman, Obschonka, Schwarz, Cohen & Nielsen, 2019).

With empowerment through entrepreneurial business, it becomes closer to experience. With the intention or desire for entrepreneurship, it will be a stepping stone at least as a hope for the realization of community welfare. Increasing productivity and ultimately winning the competition to form a particular business must create increased prosperity through entrepreneurship, especially in the home industry where there is a need for entrepreneurs to explore and expose the industry based on the encouragement of entrepreneurship so that the village can be even more advanced (Fischer, Schaeffer, Vonortas & Queiroz, 2018; Stam & Van de Ven, 2021; Malecki, 2018).

In Java itself, there are many problems that occur in a business organization from community building activities that are closely related to community welfare. Community welfare through entrepreneurship aims fighting poverty, inequality, and encouraging people to be more active and full of initiative. Community welfare itself is an effort to empower people through the realization of their potential abilities. One of the developments in human potential can be realized through community-based education activities. This activity emphasizes the importance of understanding the needs of the community and how to solve problems by the

community by taking into account the potential that exists in the environment (Bird, 2019; Čepel, M., Stasiukynas, Kotaskova & Dvorský, 2018).

In the Java region, namely East Java, which is dominant in producing food products, one of which is in several sub-districts in East Java, namely Cerem District and in Central Java, namely Purworejo District. Where the goal is through this Real Work Lecture or KKN activity from Polytechnic of Semen Indonesia to realize social change in a better or positive direction and solve social problems. The purpose of this activity is to provide assistance and counseling from the economic and technological aspects. The activity material is in the form of entrepreneurial preparation, the use of appropriate technology for the benefit of the community so that it can help the village community and provide encouragement and motivation for improving village welfare through entrepreneurship programs in the Pandemic Era (Bhawe & Zahra, 2019; De Mol, Cardon, de Jong, Khapova & Elfring, 2020).

II. IMPLEMENTATION METHODS

A. Preparation

To prepare for KKN activities in each village, preparations include:

- Gathering information on what is needed to improve the village.
- Sources of information collected on village community welfare efforts through village entrepreneurship is the chosen theme to improve the village.
- Preparations that need to be made include preparation in the selection and provision of work program sites.
- Preparation and dedication of raw materials and equipment is the first step in starting a business.
- This KKN activity is carried out online, where the welfare of the village community is carried out with several trainings and counseling online and offline. This activity provides motivation to the village community to further improve welfare through the village community entrepreneurship program.

B. Counseling

Conveying the aims and objectives of this KKN activity by conducting socialization in the form of counseling to residents about the importance of entrepreneurship in order to get an increase in village welfare and aims to realize social change in a better or positive direction and solve social problems. This activity also provides assistance and counseling from an economic aspect. Technology material activities in the form of entrepreneurship preparation, the use of appropriate technology for the benefit of the community. In addition, it also helps village communities by providing encouragement, motivation to improve village welfare through entrepreneurship programs in the pandemic era.

C. Activity Planning

The preparation of an activity plan is carried out with a certain period of time. First regarding the dissemination of planned activities through an online system, through the Whatsapp group, then using Youtube, even with posters.

Furthermore, in the form of a program that has been selected and then implemented to the village community.

- Develop an activity proposal to assist in the socialization and implementation of the work program.
- Observing the importance of holding entrepreneurship programs because the background of each community is different so that they can find out what problems occur and find ways to overcome them.
- Arrange the time of implementation of activities and ask permission from the authorities.
- Preparing equipment in providing training.
- Preparing targets and a list of parties to be used as participants in socialization and implementation.

D. Activity Implementation

The implementation method is as follows:

- Prepare facilities and infrastructure along with the equipment used.
- Conducting socialization or training to the village community about the program that has been arranged.
- The village community re-practices the results of the socialization obtained.
- Evaluating the results of work program activities.

E. Implementation Technique

The implementation of this community welfare activity was carried out using a tourorial method carried out online through videos and posters, where one of the objectives of this activity was to explore the potential of the village. The systematic implementation of this welfare activity is to provide socialization related to making crackers, milkfish brains, fertilizer, mats, jenang with simple techniques and using the recipes provided.

➤ *Management of milkfish brains Time: August 18, 2023*

- **Place:** Tambak Beras Village and Jono Village, Cerme District.
- **Step one (video tutorial method):** The people of Tambak Beras Village and Jono Village were given online material on how to make milkfish brains.
- **Step two (discussion method):** Villagers are given the opportunity to discuss through whatsapp groups and zoom about making milkfish brains.

Videos related to making milkfish brains are shared through Mrs. PKK Tambak Beras Village. Training on making milkfish brains through videos to increase entrepreneurship and village empowerment includes:

- **Basic ingredients:** The basic material used is milkfish that has been taken and ground, of course fresh and quality milkfish will make a different taste when processing fish.
- **Additional Ingredients**
 - ✓ Grated Coconut / Koya: Grated coconut that has been roasted browned after that is ground using a blender until smooth and becomes koya.
 - ✓ Fish Skin: The skin of the milkfish from the separation of the skin and fish meat, then the fish skin is used as an exterior or wrapping the brain of the milkfish.
 - milkfish brain.

- ✓ Seasoning
- Shallots
- Garlic
- Large red chili
- Cayenne pepper
- Ginger
- Sugar
- Salt
- Coriander

- *Tools*
 - Fish grinder (blender or manual grinder)
 - Blender to puree koya and spices
 - Wok and stove to make koya
 - Oven and baking sheet to bake the brains
 - Container or basin 4). Steps
 - The ground fish is mixed with all the spices and mixed with koya,
 - Stir the mixture well if it feels even,
 - Put the dough into the fish skin,
 - After that, flatten it until it is shaped and put the brain - brain on a baking sheet,
 - Put the brains into the oven,
 - Oven up to 25 minutes, the brains are ready to be served or packaged.

Fig. 1: Processed milkfish into milkfish brains

- *Corn Jenang Management Time: August 18, 2023*
 - Place: Jrahah Village, Purworejo District
 - Step one (video tutorial method): The Jrahah Village community was given online material on how to make corn jenang. Training through videos on making corn jenang to increase entrepreneurship and village empowerment.
 - Step two (discussion method): Villagers were given the opportunity to discuss the making of corn jenang through a Whatsapp group. Videos related to making corn jenang are shared through the WA group of Mrs. PKK Jrahah

Village to improve the welfare and empowerment of the village which includes:

- Basic ingredients
The basic ingredients used are fresh corn and crushed by shredding.

- Additional ingredients
- ✓ Grated coconut: Grated coconut that has been grated and uses young coconut to make it taste more savory.
- ✓ Seasoning
 - Brown sugar
 - Salt
 - Pandan
- *Tools*
 - Grater used to grate corn and coconut
 - Cauldron/pot for dissolving brown sugar
 - Basin (a place to put the dough)
 - Wok and stove (mixer)
 - Container and sieve 4). Steps
 - Combine the corn mixture and grated coconut,
 - Then squeeze or strain and take the essence,
 - Melt the brown sugar,
 - Then mix all the dough into the pan,
 - Stir until thickened and add salt to make it more savory
 - After thickening, put the jenang into the cetalan and wait until it cools and hardens,
 - Jenang is ready to be packaged and eaten.

Fig. 2: Processed results of Jenang Jagung

- *Cracker Management Time: August 18, 2023*
- Place: Banjarsari Asri Housing, Cerme District
- Step one (video tutorial method): Conduct training with the help of videos during cracker making.
- Step two (discussion method): Local residents are given the opportunity and assistance regarding making fish crackers in the Whatsapp group. Conduct training on making mujaer fish crackers through Mrs. PKK by providing video tutorials on the management of making mujaer fish crackers through videos from Youtube and shared to WAG (Whatsapp Group).
- Making mujaer fish crackers by including:
 - ✓ Basic ingredients
 - The basic ingredients used are quality tapioca flour or starch.
 - ✓ Additional ingredients
 - Tilapia Fish: Tilapia meat that has been ground until smooth.
 - Seasoning

- Garlic
- Salt
- *Tools*
 - Blender or cobek for seasoning
 - Plastic for cracker molding
 - Tempeh
 - Wok and stove
 - Steamer
- *Steps*
 - Puree the garlic,
 - Combine all ingredients into a dough,
 - Shape the dough using plastic,
 - Then steam the cracker dough until cooked,
 - After cooking, remove and drain the dough,
 - Thinly slice the cracker dough and arrange it on a plate.
 - Heat the sliced crackers in the sun until completely dry,
 - Once dry, fry the crackers.

Fig. 3: Processed results of tilapia fish crackers

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Activities to improve village welfare through entrepreneurship programs in this pandemic era are carried out individually in their respective villages and online by utilizing social media such as WhatsApp, Youtube, Zoom,

and Gmeet to develop entrepreneurship by looking at the potential of each village. Evaluation of the activities that have been carried out there are several obstacles, namely in technology. Where there are some residents who are less able to utilize or use social media technology.

IV. CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTION

Based on the results and discussion of the activities that have been carried out, several things can be concluded, including:

A. Conclusion

The conclusion from the Real Work Lecture activity with the theme "Improving Village Welfare through Entrepreneurship Programs in the Pandemic Era" where there is a lack of motivation and encouragement to improve village welfare. Through this KKN program, Polytechnic of Semen Indonesia helps villages in Cerme, Bungah and Purworejo sub-districts in Central Java to further improve village welfare through entrepreneurship programs.

B. Suggestion

It is expected to further explore village entrepreneurship activities without the limitation of activities due to the Covid-19 pandemic. Activities carried out online result in limited delivery of entrepreneurial activities to the community so that the results are less than optimal.

V. IMPLICATION MANAGERIAL

Research on "Community Service to Improve Village Welfare through Entrepreneurship Programmes in the Pandemic Era" can make various useful contributions to stakeholders, such as the government, community, and schools.

The research can provide insights to the government on the effectiveness of entrepreneurship programmes in improving village welfare amidst the pandemic. This can help them design better policies to support similar initiatives in the future. The research results can assist the government in village planning and development, by focusing resources on entrepreneurship programmes that are proven to work.

Scaled-up entrepreneurship programmes based on the results of this research can provide opportunities for village communities to increase their income, create local jobs and reduce unemployment rates. Through entrepreneurship, villagers can improve their quality of life with better access to healthcare, education and infrastructure.

This research can encourage an improved education curriculum in schools, emphasising entrepreneurship training. This can help students develop useful skills for their future. Schools can establish partnerships with village communities to engage students in real-life entrepreneurship and community service projects.

This research can also provide more accurate information on how the pandemic affects villages and entrepreneurship programmes in difficult times. This helps stakeholders in responding to the ongoing situation and ensuring that efforts to improve village welfare remain relevant and effective.

REFERENCES

- [1]. Akhmetshin, E. M., Mueller, J. E., Yumashev, A. V., Kozachek, A. V., Prikhodko, A. N., & Safonova, E. E. (2019). Acquisition of entrepreneurial skills and competences: Curriculum development and evaluation for higher education. *Journal of Entrepreneurship Education*, 22(1), 1-12.
- [2]. Al-Jubari, I., Hassan, A., & Liñán, F. (2019). Entrepreneurial intention among University students in Malaysia: integrating self-determination theory and the theory of planned behavior. *International entrepreneurship and management journal*, 15, 1323-1342.
- [3]. Apriana, D., Kristiawan, M., & Wardiah, D. (2019). Headmaster's competency in preparing vocational school students for entrepreneurship. *International Journal of Scientific & Technology Research*, 8(8), 1316-1330.
- [4]. Bhawe, N., & Zahra, S. A. (2019). Inducing heterogeneity in local entrepreneurial ecosystems: The role of MNEs. *Small Business Economics*, 52, 437-454.
- [5]. Bird, B. (2019). Toward a theory of entrepreneurial competency. In *Seminal ideas for the next twenty-five years of advances* (pp. 115-131). Emerald Publishing Limited.
- [6]. Čepel, M., Stasiukynas, A., Kotaskova, A., & Dvorský, J. (2018). Business environment quality index in the SME segment. *Journal of Competitiveness*.
- [7]. Chowdhury, F., Audretsch, D. B., & Belitski, M. (2019). Institutions and entrepreneurship quality. *Entrepreneurship theory and practice*, 43(1), 51-81.
- [8]. De Mol, E., Cardon, M. S., de Jong, B., Khapova, S. N., & Elfring, T. (2020). Entrepreneurial passion diversity in new venture teams: An empirical examination of short-and long-term performance implications. *Journal of Business Venturing*, 35(4), 105965.
- [9]. Fischer, B. B., Schaeffer, P. R., Vonortas, N. S., & Queiroz, S. (2018). Quality comes first: university-industry collaboration as a source of academic entrepreneurship in a developing country. *The Journal of Technology Transfer*, 43, 263-284.
- [10]. Listiningrum, H. D., Wisetsri, W., & Boussanlegue, T. C. H. A. B. L. E. (2020). Principal's entrepreneurship competence in improving teacher's entrepreneurial skill in high schools. *Journal of Social Work and Science Education*, 1(1), 87-95.
- [11]. LPM Universitas Muhammadiyah Gresik. (2021). *Guidebook for Real Work Lecture Even 2021*. University of Muhammadiyah Gresik.
- [12]. Lotulung, C. F., Ibrahim, N., & Tumurang, H. (2018). Effectiveness of Learning Method Contextual Teaching Learning (CTL) for Increasing Learning Outcomes of Entrepreneurship Education. *Turkish Online Journal of Educational Technology-TOJET*, 17(3), 37-46.
- [13]. Malecki, E. J. (2018). Entrepreneurship and entrepreneurial ecosystems. *Geography compass*, 12(3), e12359.

- [14]. Mas, S. R., Masaong, A. K., & Suling, A. (2021). School principal entrepreneurial competency development model to optimize generating production unit income. *Journal of Educational and Social Research*, 11(5), 109-109.
- [15]. Nasir et al. (2019). The Role of Women Farmers Group in Improving Community Welfare through Small Land Utilisation. *Journal of Community Service and Empowerment*, 391) : 1-2.
- [16]. Newman, A., Obschonka, M., Schwarz, S., Cohen, M., & Nielsen, I. (2019). Entrepreneurial self-efficacy: A systematic review of the literature on its theoretical foundations, measurement, antecedents, and outcomes, and an agenda for future research. *Journal of vocational behavior*, 110, 403-419.
- [17]. Pellegrini, M. M., Rialti, R., Marzi, G., & Caputo, A. (2020). Sport entrepreneurship: A synthesis of existing literature and future perspectives. *International Entrepreneurship and Management Journal*, 16(3), 795-826.
- [18]. Santoso, S., & Oetomo, B. S. D. (2018). Influence of motivation and self-efficacy on entrepreneurial intention to run a business. *Expert Journal of Marketing*, 6(1), 14-21.
- [19]. Saragih, Rintang. (2017). Building Creative, Innovative and Useful Enterprises through the Application of Social Entrepreneurship. *Journal of Entrepreneurship*, 2(3) : 1-2.
- [20]. Stam, E., & Van de Ven, A. (2021). Entrepreneurial ecosystem elements. *Small business economics*, 56, 809-832.
- [21]. Sukirman. (2017). Entrepreneurial Spirit and Entrepreneurial Values Increase Business Independence through Entrepreneurial Behaviour. *Journal of Economics and Business*, 20(1) : 113-132.
- [22]. Untoro, Joko. (2010). *Economics*. Jakarta: Kawah Media.